

Solubilities of Amino Acids in Ethanol + Water Mixture at different Temperatures

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The solubilities of amino acids in ethanol + water mixtures have been determined at three different temperatures to understand the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids from water to ethanol + water mixtures. The results have been interpreted in terms of structural changes in the solvent mixtures. Attempts have been made to find out the contributions of different constituent groups towards hydrophobic interactions and their variations with solvent composition.

Solubility studies have been widely utilised to understand various parameters associated with the solvation processes. Nozaki and Tanford¹ studied the solubility of amino acids in different mixed and non-aqueous solvents to understand quantitatively the role of the solvent media in unfolding the native proteins and the contributions of various groups present in proteins to cause unfolding to occur.

However, it is expected that the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids from water to various solvent mixtures will give better idea regarding structural and interaction parts of the solvent effects. The free energy of solvation of amino acids can be written as²

$$\Delta G_s^0 = \Delta G_{cav}^0 + \Delta G_{int}^0 + RT \ln \frac{RT}{V}$$

where ΔG_{cav}^0 and ΔG_{int}^0 refer to the free energy changes due to creation of cavities and interaction of solute with solvent respectively and V is the molar volume of the solvent.

With these idea in view, Dey and Lahiri³ determined the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids from water to methanol + water mixtures. As a part of our programme of systematic investigation on the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids from water to different aquo-organic binary mixtures, we report in this communication the results of our investigation on the solubility of amino acids in ethanol + water mixtures at different temperatures. The effect of increasing hydrophobic character of the solvent mixtures on the thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids may be derived from such studies. Moreover, the structural changes of the solvent mixtures due to the introduction of amino acids and their implications can be obtained from the entropy of transfer of the amino acids in aquo-ethanolic mixtures.

Results and Discussion

The free energies of transfer of amino acids from water to aquoethanolic mixtures are related to the free energies of solution of amino acids in water [ΔG_w^0 (RH[±])] and binary mixtures [ΔG_m^0 (RH[±])] and are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^0 &= \Delta G_m^0 \text{ (RH}^\pm\text{)} - \Delta G_w^0 \text{ (RH}^\pm\text{)} \\ &= -2.303 RT \log \frac{{}^s c_i}{{}^w c_i} - 2.303 RT \log \frac{{}^s f_i}{{}^w f_i} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ${}^s c_i$ and ${}^w c_i$ represent the solubility (in molar units) of amino acids in mixed solvents (s) and water (w) respectively and f terms represent activity coefficients in the respective solvents. The activity coefficients of the amino acids in mixed solvents at different temperatures are not known and difficult to determine. The method of Nozaki and Tanford¹ (subsequently used by Talukdar *et al.*⁴) in assuming activity coefficients of amino acids in mixed solvents to be equal to these in water at the same molality followed by corrections for solute-solute interactions (chiefly electrostatic) multiplying $RT \ln {}^s f_i$ by D_w/D_m (D_w and D_m being the dielectric constants of water and solvent respectively) appears to be untenable. The vapour pressure of saturated solution of amino acids in mixed solvents can not be equal to the vapour pressure of the same amount of amino acids in water. Considerable derivations from ideality are expected in mixed solvents. Moreover, the activity coefficients determined using vapour pressure measurements need no correction for solute-solute interactions involving dielectric constants. The expression for the activity coefficients of the amino acids in presence of salts derived by Kirkwood⁵ is

$$-\log \gamma = \frac{A}{D^2 T^2} \frac{R^2}{a} \mu$$

where a is the mean distance of closest approach

of the ions of the salt to the dipolar ion and R the distance between the charges of the dipolar ion, i.e. $\log \gamma \propto 1/D^2$ in case of amino acids.

Since the solubility of amino acids decreases enormously with the increase in organic solvent, solute-solute interaction terms are expected to be very small. Nozaki and Tanford¹ also observed interaction terms are not of prime importance for most of the amino acids except glycine. Therefore, instead of applying arbitrary corrections, we report ΔG_t^0 assuming f values to be unity in the corresponding states of saturated solutions in the respective solvents, i.e.

$$\Delta G_t^0 = -2.303 RT \log \frac{c_i}{w c_i} \quad (2)$$

It is well-known that ΔC_p varies with temperature and an accurate determination of ΔH

requires the measurement of solubilities over a wide range of temperatures. But the solubility values determined over a wide range of temperature may be of limited accuracy leading to an error in ΔH values. The enthalpies of solvation of amino acids (ΔH^0) have been determined from the slope of the plots of $\log C_s$ against $1/T$ assuming ΔH^0 to remain unchanged in the temperature range 288–298 K. The ΔS^0 values and thermodynamics of transfer of amino acids from water to mixed solvents have been obtained from the relations,

$$\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T \Delta S^0 \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta X_t^0 = \Delta X_m^0 (\text{RH}^\pm) - \Delta X_w^0 (\text{RH}^\pm) \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta X_m (\text{RH}^\pm)$ and $\Delta X_w (\text{RH}^\pm)$ are any thermodynamic like G, H , etc. in mixed solvents and water respectively.

TABLE I—SOLUBILITY AND FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF AMINO ACIDS IN EtOH+H₂O MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

EtOH wt %	288 K		293 K		298 K	
	C_s mol dm ⁻³	ΔG_t^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	C_s mol dm ⁻³	ΔG_t^0 kJ mol ⁻¹	C_s mol dm ⁻³	ΔG_t^0 kJ mol ⁻¹
<i>Glycine</i>						
0	3.025	0	3.180	0	3.325 (3.333)	0
8.0	2.775	0.21	2.945	0.19	3.100	0.18
16.4	2.525	0.43	2.700	0.40	2.875	0.36
25.3	1.087	2.45	1.175	2.43	1.275	2.38
34.4	0.961 6	2.74	1.050	2.70	1.150	2.63
44.0	0.838 0	3.07	0.871 0	3.16	0.912 5	3.21
54.1	0.117 5	7.78	0.131 8	7.76	0.152 5	7.64
64.7	0.075 8	8.83	0.087 1	8.77	0.100 0	8.69
76.0	0.060 0	9.39	0.077 6	9.05	0.097 5	8.75
88.6	0.011 0	13.45	0.017 8	12.64	0.028 45	11.15
100.0	0.002 9	16.65	0.005 0	15.73	0.008 50	14.79
<i>α-Alanine</i>						
0	1.64	0	1.70	0	1.87	0
8.0	1.48	0.24	1.60	0.25	1.68	0.26
16.4	1.285	0.58	1.395	0.59	1.46	0.60
25.3	0.840	1.60	0.860	1.77	0.88	1.87
34.4	0.370	3.56	0.385	3.73	0.40	3.82
44.0	0.338 5	3.77	0.370	3.82	0.39	3.88
54.1	0.150 0	3.72	0.150	5.81	0.175	5.87
64.7	0.135 0	5.98	0.150	6.02	0.160	6.09
76.0	0.018 5	10.74	0.020 5	10.87	0.022 5	10.95
87.6	0.007 7	12.82	0.010 0	12.62	0.013 0	12.31
100.0	0.002 5	15.52	0.003 6	15.11	0.005 0	14.68
<i>L-Valine</i>						
0	0.718	0	0.736	0	0.755	0
8.0	0.636	0.29	0.647	0.31	0.660	0.33
16.4	0.592	0.47	0.598	0.50	0.610	0.52
25.3	0.408	1.39	0.412	1.41	0.420	1.45
34.4	0.183	3.28	0.188 4	3.31	0.195	3.35
44.0	0.173 5	3.40	0.181 0	3.41	0.187 5	3.45
54.1	0.137 0	3.97	0.155 0	3.79	0.170 0	3.69
64.7	0.019 0	8.70	0.022 4	8.51	0.025 5	8.39
76.0	0.010 0	10.24	0.012 0	10.02	0.014 5	9.79
87.6	0.000 2	19.61	0.000 28	19.18	0.000 375	18.85
100.0	0.000 125	20.74	0.000 177 8	20.29	0.000 250	19.85

Table 1 (Contd.)

L-Leucine

0	0.174	0	0.180	0	0.186	0
8.0	0.157	0.24	0.162	0.25	0.167	0.22
16.4	0.136	0.59	0.140	0.61	0.144	0.63
25.3	0.109	1.11	0.113 5	1.12	0.118	1.13
34.4	0.048	3.08	0.052 0	3.02	0.056	2.97
44.0	0.046	3.19	0.049 0	3.17	0.054	3.06
54.1	0.043	3.35	0.046 5	3.30	0.051	3.21
64.7	0.016	5.71	0.018 7	5.52	0.021 5	5.35
76.0	0.011	6.61	0.013 2	6.37	0.016 0	6.08
87.6	0.003 5	9.34	0.004 6	8.93	0.005 9	8.55
100.0	0.003 05	9.68	0.004 1	9.21	0.005 3	8.82

L-Asparagine

0	0.218	0	0.221	0	0.226	0
8.0	0.157	0.78	0.160	0.80	0.162	0.83
16.4	0.068	2.79	0.069 5	2.83	0.071 5	2.86
25.3	0.030 45	4.71	0.031 45	4.76	0.032 45	4.81
34.4	0.011 30	7.13	0.011 65	7.18	0.012 20	7.24
44.0	0.004 88	9.10	0.005 17	9.16	0.005 45	9.24
54.1	0.002 355	10.84	0.002 52	10.91	0.002 70	10.99
64.7	0.001 124	12.62	0.001 255	12.61	0.001 40	12.60
76.0	0.000 680	13.82	0.000 783	13.76	0.000 90	13.70
87.6	0.000 350	15.41	0.000 491	15.28	0.000 50	15.15
100.0	0.000 240	16.31	0.000 312	16.00	0.000 40	15.71

L-Phenylalanine

0	0.174	0	0.177	0	0.180	0
8.0	0.158 8	0.22	0.161	0.23	0.163	0.24
16.4	0.076 0	1.98	0.077 3	2.02	0.078 5	2.06
25.3	0.063 8	2.40	0.065 6	2.42	0.067 2	2.44
34.4	0.025 6	4.59	0.026 8	4.60	0.028 0	4.61
44.0	0.020 9	5.07	0.022 3	5.05	0.023 5	5.04
54.1	0.015 8	5.74	0.017 4	5.65	0.019 0	5.57
64.7	0.004 83	8.58	0.005 5	8.46	0.006 2	8.35
76.0	0.003 64	9.26	0.004 26	9.08	0.005 0	8.88
87.6	0.002 64	10.03	0.003 20	9.78	0.003 8	9.56
100.0	0.000 68	13.28	0.000 87	12.95	0.001 1	12.63

L-Serine

0	0.453	0	0.461	0	0.47 (0.478)	0
8.0	0.411	0.23	0.417	0.25	0.422 5	0.26
16.4	0.155 5	2.56	0.160	2.58	0.165 0	2.59
25.3	0.136 0	2.88	0.141	2.89	0.146 0	2.90
34.4	0.057 0	4.96	0.060 6	4.95	0.064 0	4.94
44.0	0.047 0	5.39	0.051 3	5.36	0.054 5	5.34
54.1	0.019 55	7.52	0.022 0	7.42	0.024 35	7.34
64.7	0.016 20	7.97	0.018 7	7.82	0.021 00	7.70
76.0	0.002 87	12.12	0.003 47	11.92	0.004 10	11.75
87.6	0.000 74	15.37	0.000 92	15.16	0.001 125	14.95
100.0	0.000 10	20.16	0.000 135	19.83	0.000 180	19.50

L-Histidine

0	0.258	0	0.264	0	0.272 (0.27)	0
8.0	0.229 5	0.27	0.236	0.28	0.241 5	0.29
16.0	0.145 0	1.37	0.150	1.39	0.154 0	1.41
25.3	0.127 2	1.68	0.131 8	1.70	0.136 0	1.71
34.4	0.096 0	2.36	0.101 2	2.34	0.106 0	23.3
44.0	0.036 6	4.67	0.039 4	4.64	0.042 5	4.60
54.1	0.011 85	7.37	0.013 8	7.37	0.016 0	7.02
64.7	0.009 40	7.93	0.011 3	7.58	0.013 5	7.44
76.0	0.001 02	13.25	0.001 35	12.86	0.001 8	12.43
87.6	0.000 595	14.54	0.000 826	14.06	0.001 1	13.65
100.0	0.000 345	15.84	0.000 476	15.40	0.000 65	14.95

Fig. 1. Plots of thermodynamics parameters of glycine against wt% of ethanol: (Δ) $T\Delta S^\ddagger$, (O) ΔH^\ddagger and (\bullet) ΔG^\ddagger .

amino acids. It has been found that free energy of transfer values increase continuously with increasing organic co-solvent (Table 1) but the result definitely indicates the compensation of enthalpy and entropy terms to give a simple linear free energy changes. An initial decrease in enthalpy values of solution in the aquo-ethanolic mixtures was observed near about 8 wt% for glycine. However, enthalpy value for glycine increases afterwards, becomes maximum at about 34 wt%. There is a sharp drop in enthalpy value at 44 wt% and the enthalpy increases continuously and the variation appears to be large above 64 wt% of ethanol. In case of α -alanine, enthalpy of solution decreases continuously to become minimum at 25.3 wt% of ethanol and then increases continuously but the increase in enthalpy values becomes considerable beyond 76 wt% of ethanol. The enthalpy values for other amino acids are considerably lower compared to those of glycine and α -alanine (Table 2). The minima in enthalpy values are 25.3 wt% for L-valine, 16 wt% for L-leucine, 8 wt% for L-asparagine, L-phenylalanine, L-serine and L-histidine. The increase in enthalpy values though apparent beyond 76 wt% but the change is not so conspicuous compared to those observed in case of glycine and α -alanine.

The entropy values which are related to structural changes of the solvent mixtures in presence of amino acids are in most cases positive (Table 2). The minima (+ve) is observed at 8 and 44% wt for glycine, 34.4 and 76 wt% for α -alanine, at 34.4 wt% (slightly -ve) for L-valine, 16.4 wt% for L-leucine, L-serine and L-histidine. The entropy values are negative at low percentages initially upto 64.7 wt% for L-asparagine and upto 44 wt% for L-phenylalanine but the minima appears at 44–54 wt% and 16.4 wt% respectively. The entropy values are particularly high at higher percentages and decrease in the order, glycine > α -alanine > L-valine > L-histidine > L-leucine > L-serine > L-phenylalanine > L-asparagine.

The interpretation of thermodynamics of dissolution requires the consideration of the thermodynamics of mixed solvents and the thermodynamics of solvation of amino acids in mixed solvents. It is well-known that the replacement of H atom of glycine by different hydrophobic groups gives rise to other amino acids and the replacement naturally changes the interactions of the charged groups and hydrophobic groups with solvent molecules leading to changes in enthalpy and entropy values.

It is expected that the results should be similar to those observed in case of methanol. The thermodynamics of dissolution of amino acids in the solvent can be considered to consist of (i) rupture of bonds between solute molecules in the gaseous state ($\Delta H = +ve$ and $\Delta S = +ve$), (ii) creation of cavity in the appropriate solvent which means rupture of H bond ($\Delta H = +ve$ and $\Delta S = +ve$) and (iii) placement of solute into cavity. This is obviously a complicated process making formation of bonds between hydrophobic and hydrophilic centres of amino acids, solvent molecules and the possible orientations of the solvent molecule around the charged and hydrophobic groups of amino acids. (usually $\Delta H = -ve$ and $\Delta S = -ve$).

The second and third steps involve the rearrangement of solvent molecules with concomitant changes in Van der Waals forces like dipole-dipole, dispersion force and hydrophobic bond formation together with the alignment of solvent molecules around the charges.

Addition of ethanol enhances the structure-formation of water. This becomes maximum at about $X_2 = 0.1-0.2$ mole fraction of ethanol⁷ beyond which structural collapse begins.

The effect of addition of amino acids to the different mixed solvents means rearrangements of the solvent molecules and the formation of new bonds between amino acids and solvent molecules. It is apparent from the decreased solubilities of amino acids that the creation of cavities would be increasingly difficult in mixed solvents and formation of bond between solute-solvent will lead to gradual increase in enthalpy values.

The amino acids are characterised by the

presence of hydrophilic centres (CO_2^- , NH_3^+) and hydrophobic centres. Naturally, hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions will compete for water structure organisation, i.e. there will be specific solvation effects (dependent on the composition of the solvent mixtures) and the hydrophobic effects acting in the opposite directions^{9,10}. Specific solvation effect is greater for strongly solvated amino acid and the hydrophobic effect increases with the size of solute molecules and is maximum where maximum enhancement of water structure occurs, i.e. in the region of 0.2–0.3 mole fraction of alcohol. The hydrophobic effect increases with the size of solute and shifts the point of maximum structure-formation towards the media richer in water^{9,10}.

It is difficult to correlate the data with hydrophobic interaction (HI), but it is to be noted that the addition of small quantities of ethanol causes a weakening of the HI¹⁰. This effect is restricted to the region $0 \leq X_{\text{EtOH}} \leq 0.03$. At higher concentrations of ethanol, there is a pronounced increase in the HI which persists upto $X \simeq 0.2$ beyond which HI becomes weak¹⁰. It is to be noted that the minimum of enthalpy and entropy of mixing in EtOH+H₂O mixtures are in the region $X=0.2$ and $X = 0.3^{11}$ (in the region 34–44 wt%), i.e. the maxima in enthalpy and entropy changes of amino acids coincide with these values.

Cavity formation at higher percentages of alcohol is associated with the increased enthalpy changes as well as entropy changes which cannot be compensated for by the bond formation of amino acids in aquo-ethanolic solvent systems and the compensation of enthalpy and entropy values leads to general increase in free energy changes.

It is to be noted that hydrophobic interactions must be zero in ethanol. Thus, the thermodynamics of transfer of an amino acid relative to a standard amino acid like glycine from ethanol to aquo-ethanolic mixtures is the measure of the

contribution of the constitution group towards hydrophobic interaction, a variation of which with solvent composition can be determined from Tables 1 and 2.

Experimental

Absolute ethanol (Bengal Chemical, India) was treated with adequate quantity of preheated calcium oxide, kept overnight and distilled. It was refluxed with metallic sodium and distilled. The middle fraction was used within 24 h. Experimental details were followed as given in a previous communication³. The solubilities of amino acids were measured at 288 ± 0.01 , 293 ± 0.01 and 298 ± 0.01 K. The accuracy of solubility values was 0.3–0.6% upto 45 wt% and 0.5–0.8% at higher percentage of ethanol.

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